

ProteoForce

D4.1 Communication Plan and joint int. research

Name of project: Establishing Slovakia's First Cutting-Edge Advanced Laser Tweezers Laboratory for In-Depth Analysis of Molecular Forces in Clinically Relevant Hsp70 clients

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ABBREVIATIONS

AAM/VoR	Author accepted manuscript/version of record (VOR)
API	Application Programming Interface
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoS attack	Denial-of-service attack
DoW	The Description of Work
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	The European Research Area
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GB	Gigabyte
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
I4OC	Initiative for Open Citations
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenAIRE	European Open Science Infrastructure, for open scholarly and scientific communication.
OpenDOAR	Directory of Open Access Repositories
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
SPDX	Software Package Data Exchange
PDF	Portable Data File
PID	A persistent identifier
PMC	PubMed Central®
UI	User Interface
UPJS	Univerzita Pavla Jozefa Šafárika v Košiciach
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

SUMMARY

The communication and dissemination plan sets out a strategy to maximize the impact of the project ProteoForce, to increase its visibility, and to ensure that project outputs reach a wide audience of relevant stakeholders.

The purpose of this document is to describe the dissemination plan of the ProteoForce project. The dissemination plan belongs to the context of the WP4, which is responsible for creating of international collaborative network, dissemination, and communication, especially to the research communities and industrial organizations and companies that are relevant to the project and could potentially benefit from the outcomes of the project.

In this context, different communication means will be used to disseminate the project results (e.g., scientific publications, presentations, participation in industrial events, social media posts, etc.) and different user communities will be targeted. The communication means and methodologies, the target audience, and the various dissemination channels that will be used are described in detail in this document.

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1. INTRODUCTION: DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PRINCIPLES

The purpose of the dissemination and communication plan is to set out the key steps and activities that will ensure maximum stakeholder engagement and project awareness. Throughout this document, dissemination is referred to as the public disclosure of the results of a project across any communication means. It is the process of promoting and generating awareness about the project from the very beginning. Its aim is to make the project results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way. Communication refers to taking measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences including the broad public, while engaging in a two-way exchange of information (European Commission, 2016).

The dissemination and communication plan describes the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication” activities, which will be based:

Publication process: The ProteoForce partners will be entitled and incited to publish results in the usual scientific form. A list of relevant journals and conferences are collectively established. The Dissemination and Communication Plan will establish the publication rules and guidelines. All foreseen publications will follow a validation process.

Transparency: Relevant results and corresponding deliverables will be accessible through Zenodo.

Accessibility and knowledge management: The ambition is for ProteoForce particularly research activities to become a knowledge hub. This requires an active strategy of knowledge brokerage and structuring lessons learned. Properly structured this will provide synergies with other initiatives, avoiding duplication, strengthening impact, and delivering value for money. Three levels of dissemination are foreseen:

- Research partners/laboratories/research groups,
- broader ProteoForce research community,
- fully publicly disclosed.

Building knowledge capacity: Webinars, and seminars to support knowledge transfer and capacity development. They will target a wide range of actors and will showcase the project, share knowledge, and build partnerships. Further influence will be achieved through social media channels to broadcast the key outcomes and opportunities arising from these activities.

Engagement strategy: The Dissemination and Communication Plan will deliver a communication and engagement strategy, guidelines, graphical identity, and supporting material. The strategy will align with the principle of the Europe Recovery and Resilience Plan and EU directives to demonstrate the value-added benefits of the project and their wider social benefits. This will use include the following elements:

target audience segmentation; delivery channels including social media; calendar of events; etc.

1.1. Communication and Dissemination

We plan to communicate our findings to the scientific community and the general public through a variety of platforms, such as:

- **Publications:** Our research findings will be published in high-impact, peer-reviewed journals. These will be accessible to the global scientific community, fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration.
- **Conferences and Symposia:** Our team will attend and present findings at relevant scientific conferences and symposia, both locally and internationally. This will provide opportunities for discussions and collaborations with other experts in the field.
- **Public Lectures and Outreach Activities:** We plan to host public lectures and participate in science outreach activities to engage with the general public. This will help to increase public understanding and interest in our research.
- **Social Media:** We also plan to utilize social media to reach a broader audience and engage in real-time interactions.
- **Press Releases and Media Engagement:** We will work with media to disseminate our findings and their implications, thereby reaching a wider audience beyond the scientific community.

1.2. Commercialization and Technology Transfer.

To ensure the commercialization of our project's outputs, we will collaborate with industry partners to develop marketable applications based on our research. We will collaborate with university experts to facilitate the patenting process and explore licensing opportunities. Details will be addressed in the project in **WP1, Task 1.1. Quality assurance and risk management and D1.1 Data Management Plan and Project Quality Plan**. In addition, if needed, we will seek funding from commercialization grants or innovation competitions to support the development of prototypes and market testing.

1.3. Exploitation of Project Results.

Even after the project reaches its conclusion, we envision a vibrant and continuous utilization of its results. The research data will be preserved in a repository that adheres to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, ensuring it remains accessible and usable to the wider scientific community. It will be addressed

in **WP1, Task 1.1. Quality assurance and risk management and D1.1 Data Management Plan and Project Quality Plan**. Furthermore, the methods and protocols we develop throughout our project will be shared openly via specialized publications and platforms designed for sharing scientific procedures, contributing to a broader scientific knowledge base. Building upon this, the partnerships and collaborations formed during the project will act as springboards for future research and innovation in related domains, ensuring a continuous ripple effect of our work. In the event that our project involves investment in research infrastructure, we're committed to its sustained usage and upkeep. We plan to offer access to our research infrastructure to other researchers and institutions, either on a complimentary basis or for a nominal fee. This will support their research endeavors while also generating the necessary funds for the maintenance of the facility. Concurrently, we will actively pursue grants or other sources of funding geared toward the preservation and enhancement of such research infrastructure. Through these strategic initiatives, we seek to ensure the longevity and ongoing impact of our project beyond its original timeframe.

1.4. Use and protection of intellectual property rights.

The project's IPR strategy focuses on protecting and leveraging intellectual property rights (IPR) to ensure the commercial utilization of project results. Collaborating with legal and patent offices at TIP-UPJS (<https://www.upjs.sk/pracoviska/tip/tip-upjs/>), the team will determine patent-worthy results and file them promptly. They will explore technology transfer and licensing agreements to protect and exploit intellectual property. Before commercialization, the team will conduct technical and market analysis to identify potential partners and negotiate licensing terms. The IPR management strategy will balance openness with protection, potentially delaying certain findings until patent protection is secured. Overall, our IPR management will be addressed in the project in **WP1, Task 1.1. Quality assurance and risk management and D1.1 Data Management Plan and Project Quality Plan**.

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN - INITIAL VERSION

2.1. Target audience segmentation

In the following, the initial version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (in short, DCP), is explained. All the activities presently imagined for the project, and the normal rules to carry them out, are here outlined.

The audience for the project topics has been segmented into 4 work groups (WP 1 - 4), depending on their role and possible interactivity with the project:

WP1 - Experimental research on bio-constructs for optical tweezers, lab Installation, Management - The proposed project in Slovakia aims to create a single-molecule laser optical tweezers force laboratory focusing on biophysics and

nanotechnology. The laboratory will use advanced laser-based techniques to manipulate molecules with precision, allowing researchers to study molecular interactions. The facility will attract interdisciplinary collaborations and contribute to Slovakia 's research landscape, enhancing its competitiveness in the global scientific community. To this end, unique laser optical tweezers with multistream microfluidics and three-color confocal fluorescence (C-trap, Lumicks Ltd., Netherlands) for correlative quantitative measurements will be purchased and installed. To promote open science principles and data sharing, WP1 will prepare a project quality plan (PQP) and data management plan (DMP).

WP2 - Single-molecule Mechanics of Hsp70 clients - Activities involve pursuing high- and low-risk research queries, with high-risk questions potentially leading to significant scientific breakthroughs but less meaningful results. Investigates clinically relevant proteins and Hsp70 chaperones, focusing on their potential clinical implications, and investigates the interaction between membrane proteins and Hsp70 chaperones, revealing significant implications for biological processes and disease states. The objective aims to produce high-quality research papers and obtain funding for continued and expanded research, ensuring the longevity and significance of the research project.

WP3 - Research on selected Protein Targets based on national collaborative network and Training for early-stage researchers - WP3 aims to promote collaboration and knowledge sharing in Slovakia. Establishing partnerships with national stakeholders and research institutions to confirm progress is required. The achievement of this objective will be measured by the frequency and quality of knowledge exchange activities and publications resulting from these collaborations.

WP4 - Research on selected Protein Targets based on international collaborative network, dissemination and communication - WP4 aims to contribute to the national and European research landscape by targeted communication of project outcomes. The major focus is on actively participating in research events and collaborations at both national and European levels. The success of this objective will be verified through the organization's involvement in these events and partnerships. Furthermore, the evaluation will assess the impact of the research findings on the scientific community, as measured by citations of the research work and invitations to present the research at conferences or seminars.

2.2. The actual Dissemination and Communication plan

The actual Dissemination and Communication plan which includes defined chapters and covers all the D&C is shown in the following table 1

TOOL	PURPOSE	AUDIENCE	DUE	QUANTIFIED TARGETED
Project Graphical Identity	A Graphical Identity for the ProteoForce project (logo and general branding colour schemes, for templates, the social media, mail signatures.	All		-
Publications on project's social media	LinkedIn, and Facebook will be considered as main dissemination channels.	All groups		KPIs see section. 7.1
Events	ProteoForce Events List" regularly updated	All groups		"ProteoForce Events List" will be established and regularly updated
Deliverables	List of most important deliverables that are relevant to the submitted project	All groups		
Webinars / seminars / workshops	Participation in conferences and other events where partners will present.	All groups		Short webinars - 1-1.5 hours An in-person seminar - duration of at least 1 full day
Scientific publications	Involves proactively coordinating the project team's participation in various conferences and seminars.	All groups		Completed attendances of conferences (10x)

2.2.1. Project graphical identity

The project's graphical identity is under the developing process and will be reported in all official project documents, including deliverables.

It will include:

- Colour branding
- Logo
- Fonts to be used in documents
- Templates
- A basic E-Mail signature.

2.2.2. Publications on project's social media

The contents to be published on social media accounts will have to be approved following the standard procedure for general publications. The accompanying text can be published by the social media master partner, upon previous consent by the coordinator. All partners are encouraged to reshare on their social media (also with personal accounts) and/or websites the news and documents published by the project, and to give data about the impact of their posts. The social media activated are:

- Facebook
- LinkedIn

2.2.3. Events

In order to select the events where the partners should take part, and take materials concerning the project, a “ProteoForce Events List” is established and regularly updated by the dedicated person will collaborate by giving information on possible events.

In this Excel file, the following information is collected for each event:

- Name of Event
- Priority: the partners are asked to evaluate what the priority to give to this event in order to try to maximize the impact by optimizing the effort.
- Date of start of event and Date of end of event
- Physical/Online/Hybrid: if available, information on the type of participation requested.
- Website: where possible, the link to obtain fresh info about the event
- Location: where the event will be held (in case, “online”)
- Type of audience: scientific (what sector), industrial (what sector), general (what composition), etc.
- ProteoForce lectures/papers: in case a presentation is given, details on the topic (e.g., “Generic project presentation” or a specific topic)
- ProteoForce lecture/paper date: when the presentation will happen
- Presenter: who is going to present
- Reference partner: the partner who will be coordinating the participation
- Attendees: expected number of attendees

The tool will be used all along the project, by updating the lines (the upcoming events) and reassessing the priorities continuously.

2.2.4. Deliverables

Deliverables include:

- DMP – Data Management Plan,
- PQP – Project Quality Plan.
- The Interim Report (IR)
- Publications,

- Service / product
- Reports

The implementation and achievements of the project is submitted at the mid-term of project implementation, and the Final report (FR) on the achievements of the project is presented at the end of the project implementation. The access and dissemination are planned to be either P= public or N= non-public, limited only to executors for reporting purposes. Delivery will be expressed as project implementation month.

Table 2 - List of deliverables

Deliverable number	Deliverable	WP	Type	Access and dissemination	Method of verification	Delivery
D1.1	DMP and PQP	NV1	Report	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	6
D1.2	Interim Report	NV1	Report	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	15
D1.3	Lab installation	NV1	Report	N	Procurement documents and in D1.4 Final Report	17
D1.4	Final report (FR)	NV1	Report	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	30
D2.1	Proteins for tweezers	NV2	Report	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	15
D2.2	Chaperone microfluidics	NV2	Publications	P	Published open access (Zenodo)	30
D2.3	Grant submissions	NV2	Report	N	Documents and D1.4 Final Report	30
D3.1	Interim Networking	NV3	Report	P	Details in D1.2 Interim Report, Publications	15
D3.2	Training activity	NV3	Report	P	Details in D1.4 Final Report	25
D3.3	Networking activity	NV3	Report	P	Details in D1.4 Final Report	30
D4.1	Communication Plan and joint int. research	NV4	Report	P	Details in D1.2 Interim Report, Publications	7
D4.2	10x Conferences Attendance	NV4	Report	P	Details in D1.4 Final Report	30
D4.3	Summary of Commun. and Dissemination	NV4	Report	P	Details in D1.4 Final Report	30

2.3. Webinars / seminars / workshops

These will be special dissemination seminars and presentations, connected to the project, like webinars or in-person seminars, on specific project-related topics, with partners' contributions and selected external speakers.

In particular, at least the following events will be organised:

- 2 short webinars per year. These will be organized directly by the one of WP leaders, will have a duration of 1-1.5 hours (1 speaker), and will be used to address specific topics within the project's scope.
- An in-person seminar around mid-term, with 3 speakers, duration of at least 1 full day. This will be hosted in a convenient venue where interesting labs or field visits can be organised for participants.
- A final in-person event - the final conference will be organized at the end of the project, as a main dissemination event showcasing the successes achieved over the three years of the project. The details of the event (type of event, audience, keynote speakers...) will be determined during the project.

2.4. Scientific publications

Involves proactively coordinating the project team's participation in various conferences and seminars, focusing on presenting research findings, facilitating knowledge exchange, and establishing valuable connections. The selected conferences include both national and international events organized by prominent European societies such as EBSA (European Biophysical Societies' Association), FEBS (Federation of European Biochemical Societies), and EMBO (European Molecular Biology Organization), among others.

3. RULES FOR PUBLICATION

All partners are requested to be proactive in bringing information about the project, its approach, and results to the biggest possible audience. This means that publications are welcome at any time, provided they respect the basic rules that will make them useful for the project's cause.

All publications will have to:

- Agreed in advance with the project coordinator
- Prepared by the relevant partners considering the need for dissemination but also the necessary confidentiality to guarantee successful exploitation of project activities (e.g., patenting when applicable)
- Respect project branding guidelines
- Respect third-party copyrights (for instance, for pictures)
- Approved actively or passively (when relevant deadlines for consortium editing or opposing expire) by the consortium, through its ExCom and the Coordinator,

- Whenever possible and to a reasonable extent, be followed up and evaluated in terms of apparent impact (audience, views, etc.) and also qualitatively in terms of interest raised

4. MATERIALS FOR PHYSICAL DISTRIBUTION

Some material will be produced during the project to be shown and in some cases distributed to interested people in physical events. The latter may be informative material (leaflets, for instance) but may also be small gadgets that carry at least the project logo and thus might attract people to search for more information later. The informative material will also be used in its digital version for other uses.

4.1. Leaflet(s)

Leaflets will be produced both in pdf and in print. They will generally be in A5 size, two-sided. All this material will be available in electronic or physical form for download from and distributed at physical events. As a general «lean» approach, though, printed copies will be limited in number and digital downloads will be encouraged to reduce paper waste. QR codes will be offered to scan, with a direct link to the downloadable materials.

If a partner needs to print a specific leaflet, the printable files will be made available (InDesign format).

4.2. Roller banner(s)

Roller banners, or rollups, are self-standing “vertical” elements (typically 2 m high, 0.85 m wide) that usually show rather generic info about the project, for instance, the logo of the project and the partners, diagrams with an explanation of the project’s workflow and basic principles, images showing devices or parts, etc., accompanied by simple text that can be read in a short time (e.g., while walking in front of a booth). It is planned to print initially a generic roller banner with the basic information about the project, that will be used along the project. At least one more roller banner will be prepared, after midterm, with some highlights of results obtained until then.

4.3. Poster(s)

Posters can be of different approach. A poster could just show the project logo or research partners. Others could be more verbose, and explain more about the project approach, specific results, etc. It is believed that at least 3-4 different posters may be needed for exhibiting in a booth or as poster presentations in some event. WP4/WP1 will take care of preparing the graphic files for the posters and printing those needed for the events but all partners will be able to access the printable files and use them in events where they go on their own.

4.4. Consumables

Gadgets will be considered, to be distributed at exhibitions. Examples: pens, bags, USB sticks with project info, etc. The gadgets will have the project's logo and if possible, should be in line with the project's approach, recalling sustainability aspects.

5. TRAINING

Training is seen as an important part of dissemination, as it can improve awareness about the project topics, and at the same time, especially for young researchers or industrial employees, it can create durable networks that will likely grow in the future as the trained people advance in their careers. For already experienced researchers and industrial employees, the knowledge gained in the training about the project topics will be useful to steer strategic decisions in the direction of a larger use of thermoelectric materials and waste heat recovery devices.

The training activity within the ProteoForce project aims in fact to ensure the transfer of high-value knowledge already present within the partners and that will be generated by the project to promote learning opportunities and building capacities with and for young scientists.

The plan is to make use of established and new training activities, to funnel knowledge to students, young engineers, and experts. At the beginning of the activity for training a strategic document on how to present, promote, call, recruit, and orient and mentor young students and researchers into the project will be prepared.

6. NETWORKING

The achievement of Objective SO7 will be evaluated by assessing the frequency and quality of knowledge exchange activities and publications resulting from the established collaborations. Task 3.3 - Effective Collaboration as the Result of Networking Activity involves conducting joint research with partners, providing data analysis, and submitting manuscripts to prestigious journals. The impact of these collaborations on knowledge dissemination, knowledge exchange events, and resulting publications will demonstrate the success of this objective. Deliverable D3.3 - Networking Activity, described in D1.4 Final Report (Month 30), will provide a comprehensive summary of the knowledge exchange activities and publications resulting from the collaborations, supporting the evaluation process.

7. CONTINUOUS EVALUATION OF D&C PERFORMANCE

7.1. KPIS

KPIs are "a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective". Although they are not the same as metrics, in the case of measuring the performance of a website or social media that is normal. To assess the dissemination, ProteoForce

WP4 will collect data from social media and will compare some selected KPIs to chosen reference values that the project expects to meet over the years. A list of the KPIs imagined, with their reference values, is given in Table 3.

Table 3 KPIs considered for D&C activities.

TOOL	KPI	REFERENCE VALUE
LinkedIn	Followers	Year 1: 20 End: 500
Facebook	Followers	Year 1: 50 End: 2000
Webinars/seminars/workshops	Audience	30
Other publications	Reach	More than 2000

All partners will be required to enter data there if they post something related to the project. Each item will be evaluated in terms of “audience” and of “views”. The former refers to the number of potential contacts, the latter to the feedback on actual clicks, or visualizations, by some contacts in the audience. For a LinkedIn page or private account, it is the number of followers at the date of the post and reported by LinkedIn’s analytics. The number of views will be evaluated after a certain period from the post, depending on the media used (30 days for social media posts, etc.).

8. WP MEETINGS

To keep track of the activities and their performance, and steer them during the project, the WP main partners will be called to meet, normally online but in-person meetings are also possible. These include

- the WP leader
- the other WP or Task leader, as needed
- the other partner responsible for social media accounts
- the coordinator

9. UPDATE OF THE DCP

A review of the DCP will be undertaken at least at:

- Midterm
- End of project (for “legacy” activities)

In case urgent systemic issues affect dissemination or communication, in one or more activities, an urgent review will be asked by the WP/Task Leader upon agreement.